

ANNELI SARHIMAA
Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz

AURELIJA TAMOŠIŪNAITĖ
Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz

Hungarian data sets in the ELDIAdatabank

1. Introduction

This overview provides a short description of the Hungarian data sets available within the ELDIAdatabank. The ELDIAdatabank is a digital databank containing all empirical materials collected during the EU FP-7 research project ELDIA (European Language Diversity for All). ELDIA was an international, interdisciplinary project coordinated by the University of Mainz, Germany, and conducted by experts in applied linguistics and sociolinguistics, law, social studies, and statistics in 2010–2013. The overarching aim was to contribute to a better understanding of how local, national, and international (vehicular) languages interact in contemporary Europe, and to enhance the reconceptualization, re-evaluation, and promotion of individual and societal multilingualism.

The empirical data were collected in eight countries from speakers of thirteen Finno-Ugric minority languages, representing three branches of the language family: Finnic (Finnish, Meänkieli, Kven, Karelian, Veps, Estonian, Võro, Seto; see Sarhimaa 2019), Sámi (North Sámi) and Ugric (Hungarian). For Hungarian, two minority communities were studied, namely in Austria and in Slovenia. In addition to the primary study populations, that is, minority groups whose languages were at stake, a control group representing all other citizens of the countries where the investigated minorities live was surveyed and interviewed, as well.

The results of ELDIA have been published in case-specific reports (for reports on Hungarian, see Berényi-Kiss et al. 2013 and Kolláth & Gróf 2013), in an overview report (Laakso et al. 2013), and as a toolkit supervising end users in creating and using the European Language Vitality Barometer (EuLaViBar) (Spiliopoulou Åkermark et al. 2013). The reports and the toolkit are available online at the PHAIDRA repository <<https://phaidra.univie.ac.at/o:80789>>. A book placing the project results in wider academic and language-political contexts appeared in 2016 (Laakso et al. 2016). An overview of the Finnic data sets in the ELDIAdatabank is available in Sarhimaa (2019).

The following sections provide a general overview of the Hungarian data sets and detail the methodological decisions pertaining to empirical data collection. The general description of data collection tools and their design, sampling procedure, and principles behind data processing and editing have been largely adopted (with minor modifications) from Sarhimaa (2019). Yet, the discussion of case-specific characteristics and differences here concerns only the Hungarian data.

2. An overview of the Hungarian data sets

The ELDIAdatabank contains two kinds of data: the statistical data collected with a large-scale questionnaire survey and interviews carried out with speakers of the investigated minority languages and with representatives of the control groups. The databank consists of two major parts: the minority language target group database and the control group database. The Hungarian data sets available in the databank are summarized in Table 1.

Case study	Number of questionnaires distributed		Number of questionnaires returned		Response rate in %		Number of interviews		Interview material (hours:minutes)	
	Target group	Control group	Target group*	Control group*	Target group	Control group	Indiv.	Group	Indiv.	Group
Hungarian in Austria	573	608	200	120	34.9	19.7	8	8	14:48	07:07
Hungarian in Slovenia	1000	1000	294	195	29.4	19.5	12	8	06:03	07:44
In total	1573	1608	494	315	31.4	19.58	20	16	20:51	14:51

Table 1. The Hungarian data sets within the ELDIAdata databank

The Hungarian data sets are represented by two case studies: Hungarian in Austria and Hungarian in Slovenia. As Table 1 shows, both Hungarian data sets are complete: they consist of the target (minority) and the control group database, and each database contains the statistical and the interview data. In comparison to other empirical data sets within ELDIAdata databank, the data set for Hungarian in Slovenia contains the largest number of individual interviews.

It is important to note that information on Hungarian datasets presented in Table 1 deviates slightly from the summary provided in the ELDIA overview report (Laakso et al. 2013: 31). More specifically, the total number of returned questionnaires and the response rate for the control group have been updated for Hungarian in Austria. For Hungarian in Slovenia, Table 1 provides more accurate data on the number of focus group interviews, and the overall length of both individual and group interview material.

3. Data collection tools

The new empirical data for all ELDIA case studies, including Hungarian, were collected using the following tools:

- a unified survey questionnaire designed for the minorities;
- a unified survey questionnaire designed for the control groups;
- a semi-structured matrix for focus group interviews with minority stakeholder and speaker groups;
- a semi-structured matrix for focus group interviews with selected representatives of the control groups consisting of politicians, authorities, and representatives of media;
- a semi-structured matrix customised to be case-specific for interviews with individual speakers of the minority language at issue.

3.1. Questionnaire survey

The questionnaire survey among the investigated minority communities served as the main means for collecting new information on the current use and the current state of the investigated target languages. The survey sought to provide a broad and general insight into the state and the use of the investigated languages in a way that also would facilitate generalizable comparisons between the minority groups.

The minority language questionnaire was structured around the following main topics:

- Part A. Personal background information on the respondent
- Part B. Background information on the respondent's language use
- Part C. The respondent's language skills (minority language, majority language, other languages)
- Part D. The respondent's use of minority, majority, and other language(s) in different domains

Part E. Language attitudes and the respondent's desire to use languages

Part F. Public language use vs. private language use

Part G. Consumption and active use of languages by the respondent in different media

There were 63 questions in the minority questionnaire, but as there was a high number of sub-questions, the total number of questions was well over 300. The statistical datasets included in the databank contain only variables derived from the closed questions of the survey questionnaire; the variables total exactly 340.

The control group survey contained the same primary topics as the minority language survey, with the exception that Part F "Public language use vs. private language use" was omitted. The contents of the control group questionnaire were largely the same as those of the minority group questionnaire; however, some questions not relevant for majority language speakers were omitted and some questions were formulated differently. The control group survey questionnaire included 47 questions. Due to the large number of sub-questions, the variables in the control group statistical data set total 280.

3.2 Interviews

The ELDIA interview design aimed primarily at completing the survey data with in-depth qualitative insights into the themes covered by the survey. The interviews also offered the researchers the possibility of collecting information that would shed some new light on the case-specific research gaps that had been identified in ELDIA desk research. The original plan was to conduct eight individual interviews with members of the minority, eight focus group interviews with members of the minority, and three focus group interviews with representatives of society at large.

Individual interviews with members of the minorities were conducted in four age groups (18–29; 30–49; 50–65; and over 65). Focus group interviews followed the same sampling strategy, with the exception that the 30–49 age group was divided into two groups with a group of women and a group of men interviewed separately, in order to obtain a wider perspective on the current parental generation. According to the project design, the three minority focus groups should have covered (i) minority politicians and civil servants belonging to the investigated minority group, (ii) minority activists and (iii) representatives of the minority media. For Hungarian in Austria, however, it was possible to conduct only one focus group interview with minority activists, whereas the data set for Hungarian in Slovenia includes one combined focus group interview with minority activists and representatives of the minority media. As a result, each Hungarian data set contains six focus group interviews with members of the minority.

The original data collection design included two focus groups involving representatives of the control group: one for politicians and civil servants dealing with (minority-)language matters, and one for representatives of the majority-language media. According to the project design, 6–8 people should have been recruited for the focus group interviews. Nevertheless, in both Hungarian case studies it was difficult to implement this recommendation due to challenges pertaining to interviewee recruitment. Therefore, some focus group interviews (namely, with representatives of the majority media in Slovenia, and with politicians and civil servants in Austria) include only two informants. As per original project design, each Hungarian data set includes two focus group interviews with the representatives of the control group.

All focus group interviews followed a joint thematic interview template that was modified to meet the case-specific needs. The main themes were the interviewee's bilingualism or multilingualism, their use of different languages in everyday life and views on bilingualism or multilingualism as being either an asset or a problem. The interviewees were also asked about their perception of the term 'minority' and their opinion of the role of language in an individual's identity; for example, whether knowing the minority language is necessary for identification as a member of a given minority. Yet another issue was the perception of the investigated minority and its language by the society, the role of the investigated

minority language in the society at issue as well as the role of societal diversity in general. Special attention was also drawn to mapping the interviewees' opinions concerning the responsibility of society in maintaining and revitalising the investigated minority language and on their views concerning the future of the minority language in a ten-year perspective.

According to the project design, the individual interviews were conducted with one male and one female per age group, resulting in eight individual interviews per case study. Such design strategy was followed for Hungarian in Austria, whereas for Hungarian in Slovenia more than two informants were interviewed for some age groups, resulting in twelve individual interviews. The interviews were designed to collect in-depth information on four thematic fields: mother tongue; other languages; attitudes towards multilingualism; and languages and modernisation. The interview format was semi-structured in the sense that the topics were predefined but it was left to the interviewer to formulate the questions in a way that will be experienced as maximally "natural" in the interview situation and to ask further questions as suitable in the communication situation.

4. Principles for identifying survey respondents and interviewees

Concurrent sample surveys were conducted in each country to obtain information on the target populations (minority language groups) and the corresponding majority populations (control groups). Originally, the idea was to obtain about 300 responses from each survey population. This sampling goal, however, was reached only for target (minority) population in Slovenia. In Austria, despite higher response rates, the final number of minority respondents amounted to 200, whereas the final number of control group respondents remained significantly below the sampling target in both Austria and Slovenia.

Ideally, the sampling design should have been a true random sample in each country and study population. However, the project team was aware that in some countries there are no proper ways to carry out real probability sampling methods among the study populations. This was particularly the case for the study on Hungarian in Austria, where due to legislation on disclosure control it was not possible to get access to official population registers. All researchers involved in sample selection and data collection co-operated closely with the project statistician Kari Djerf (University of Helsinki) and with Karl Pajusalu (University of Tartu) who was in charge for the fieldwork in ELDIA. The best possible solution was sought for each case study to assure the maximal comparability of the obtained data. Ultimately, random sampling could be applied in Hungarian case studies in one form or another. Yet, in both case studies, especially in the study concerning Hungarian in Austria, the obtained data show age as well as gender bias.

In an ideal case, all study populations should have been divided equally by gender and four rough age categories (18–29, 30–49, 50–64, and 65+) with as much variation as possible in terms of the demographic background of the respondents. In the case study concerning Hungarian in Slovenia, it was possible to obtain the intended division by gender and age, as the sampling frame was based on an official register. In the case study on Hungarian in Austria, however, this division was not maintained, as no official register was available for sampling. In Austria, the actual sampling frame for minority respondents was based on membership registers of Hungarian organizations, while the respondents for the control group survey were randomly selected by the Austrian Postal Service.

According to the initial interview design, the interviewees in the age cohort focus groups should have been selected mainly from those who had returned the survey questionnaire; the idea was to ask in the questionnaire whether the respondent will allow a further contact and is willing to give an interview. In practice, however, this recommendation was followed to a certain extent only in the case study concerned with Hungarian in Austria. For Hungarian in Slovenia, most (if not all) interviewees were selected by the responsible research team, and the selection was based on researchers' scholarly

knowledge of the local circumstances and personal networks within the minority and the majority communities. For Hungarian in Austria, Facebook as well as electronic mailing lists were used to complement the selection of interviewees recruited via mail survey.

When compiling the minority focus groups, participants with at least a receptive (“passive”) command of the minority language were preferred. The control group interviewees were selected from people engaged in decision-making bodies, an additional criterion was that they had shown some interest – positive or negative – to matters concerning the investigated minorities.

5. Timeframe of data collection

According to the original project plan, the new data were to be gathered in late 2010 to early 2011 using mail surveys addressed to randomly selected respondents, and by semi-structured focus group and individual interviews which should have taken place during the spring of 2011. The case studies involving Hungarian in Austria and Slovenia largely followed this timeframe. After the pilot in August 2010, the fieldwork in Austria was conducted between September 2010 and May 2011. In Slovenia, the data were collected between November 2010 and April 2011.

6. Digital formats of the data sets, data processing, and editing

All the data collected by the surveys and tape- and video-recorded in the interviews were processed into a digital format. The interviews were transcribed employing a rough transcription system.

The survey data sets include only the results of the closed questions, since only these could provide numerical values automatically. The entire ELDIAdata minority-language database contains in total 3,388 individual records, of which 494 records concern Hungarian data; the language-specific data sets include 340 variables each. The entire control group database contains in total 1,460 records from seven countries, of which 120 represent Austria and 195 represent Slovenia; each country-specific data set covers 280 variables.

All values in all data sets have been checked by statisticians. In the databank the survey-questionnaire data are stored in a format which allows for computer-based processing with a wide variety of statistical applications.

The basic data sets and analysis were programmed using the SAS software. Later on, the data sets were transformed into the SPSS data format as well. After the questionnaires were scanned (or entered into the required form manually), a substantial effort had to be taken to edit all data sets as uniformly as possible for comparative analyses. The editing was conducted by the ELDIA statistics team in Helsinki. The first edition round was completed in September–October 2011, the second round which provided the final data files now included in the ELDIAdata was conducted in June–July 2013.

7. Availability of the ELDIA data and the conditions for using these in further research

The ELDIAdata databank is managed by the Board of Administration consisting of representatives of the research institutions that participated in ELDIA. All ELDIAdata data sets can be viewed and accessed via *Zenodo* repository at <<https://zenodo.org/communities/eldiadata>>. The databank is available for research purposes only and only per a written request addressed to the Board. The request form and the usage declaration form can be downloaded from the PHAIDRA repository <<https://phaidra.univie.ac.at/o:1048567>>.

References

- Berényi-Kiss, Hajnalka, Johanna Laakso & Angelika Parfuss 2013: *Hungarian in Austria: ELDIA case-specific report*. Studies in European Language Diversity 22. Available at: <<https://phaidra.univie.ac.at/open/o:308806>>
- Kolláth, Anna & Annamária Gróf 2013: *Hungarian in Slovenia: ELDIA case-specific report*. Studies in European Language Diversity 28. Available at: <<https://phaidra.univie.ac.at/open/o:356605>>
- Laakso, Johanna, Anneli Sarhimaa, Sia Spiliopoulou Åkermark & Reetta Toivanen 2013: *Summary of the Research Project ELDIA (European Language Diversity for All). Abridged version of the original English-language report*. Available at: <<https://fedora.phaidra.univie.ac.at/fedora/get/o:304813/bdef:Content/get>>
- Laakso, Johanna, Anneli Sarhimaa, Sia Spiliopoulou Åkermark & Reetta Toivanen 2016: *Towards openly multilingual policies and practices. Assessing minority language maintenance across Europe*. Linguistic Diversity and Language Rights 11. Bristol: Multilingual Matters.
- Spiliopoulou Åkermark, Sia, Johanna Laakso, Anneli Sarhimaa, Reetta Toivanen, Eva Kühhirt & Kari Djerf 2013: *EuLaViBar Toolkit*. Wien: ELDIA. Available at: <https://phaidra.univie.ac.at/detail_object/o:301101>
- Sarhimaa, Anneli 2019: Finnic data sets in the ELDIAdata databank. In S. Björklöf & S. Jantunen (eds.) *Multilingual Finnic: Language contact and change*. Uralica Helsingiensia 14. Helsinki. 367–377.